

Literature review
By Neharika Verma

**Topic: Blended learning: information technology as a teaching tool for 1-2-year-olds by
Neharika Verma**

1. Introduction

I have observed increased use of information technology with tamariki in early childhood centers by kaiako. In my own experience, I have noticed that teachers use electronic devices like tablets, phones, or laptops during mat times, play times, or generally in the class to introduce alternative learning experiences. I have also been using information technology for such practices. I aim to investigate the influence of my current practices of using electronic devices, gather information on using information technology with tamariki, and implement new strategies based on these findings. Some studies have found that parents believe too much screen time causes attention problems, poor concentration, the constant need for screening, and anxiety. Data collected by Gjelaj, Buza, Shatri, & Zabeli, (2020) says “Despite the countless benefits, parents associate technology use with socializing problems, too much screen time, sleeping problems, physical development delays while they also think that children miss an outdoor play with their peers and they even develop behavioral problems” (p.173). While other studies (Wood, Specht, Willoughby, & Mueller 2008) mention that parents believe that in the modern world, it is important that tamariki are aware of what information technology is and know how to use it before starting school, and not have any knowledge of it may result in their child lacking behind in school. Research by Gjelaj, Buza, Shatri, & Zabeli, (2020) summarize the data by saying that “Around 43 percent of parents declared they are firm believers that children using technology will promote their school readiness. However, around 57 percent of them do not support this relationship” (p.173)

This literature review shall help me understand the views and impact of information technology on children from multiple perspectives, reflect on my own use of information technology and devise strategies for the intervention stage of this research.

2. Context

There are several common themes in the data that I have observed throughout my literature review:

The use of ICT in early childhood education (ECE) has grown tremendously over the past decade. Several studies have been conducted on the topic, with a number of them **strongly advocating** for the use of IT in ECE, when integrated within the everyday learning and teaching context of early childhood education. **It can be observed that these authors and studies strongly focus on the positive impact of using IT in early childhood centres.**

Many of these publications certainly argue for the use of IT in early childhood education when incorporated into the regular learning and teaching context of early childhood education (Colbert, 2006; Jordan, 2006; Lee & O'Rourke, 2006; Ramsey et al., 2006). These studies emphasise, in particular, how IT may serve as an excellent tool for making transparent and ongoing early children's learning. Siraj-Blatchford and Whitebread (2003) argues that it is important for children to have access to “meaningful and purposeful” IT experiences since these children live in highly modernised technological world and teachers have the responsibility to provide opportunities for them to engage in technological experiences.

Colbert (2006) describes one example of this, in which children's tale telling was observed to increase in complexity after being published in book form. Tamariki presented their stories and either drew or used digital images to illustrate them, which they then saved and placed into their books (Pohio, 2009, p14). Pohio, 2009, also concludes in their research that ICT supports teaching and learning with reflection on *Te Whaariki*. Another study conducted by Ramsey et al. (2006) also advocates for using IT tools such as laptops and tablets to help facilitate learning across multiple domains including mathematics and science, social studies, art and music. Similarly, Herodotou (2018) noted beneficial consequences on the development of literacy, as well as beneficial effects on math, science, problem-solving, and self-efficacy, and how the effectiveness of these outcomes depends on design elements and the presence of teachers in the classroom (will be contd in upcoming themes). Moreover, in a research by Cavus & Ibrahim, (2017), who developed their own interactive application for young children to enhance their English speaking skills, the authors conclude that their has been a significant improvement in children's listening, vocabulary, comprehension and pronunciation skills while learning English as a second language. Furthermore, this enhances

their self identity as children gain confidence in their language and literacy skills. I wonder if it supports their mana and recognises them as “confident and competent” learners according to Ministry Of Education, (2017). In the paper by Pohio, 2009, the author quotes Ramsey, 2006 to support their claim that “ICT was [is] integrated with the implementation of Te Whāriki” (p.2). This notion of integration is also explicitly stated by Ministry of Education (2005), *“ICT use in early childhood education does not imply “computers for children.” It is about how children, educators, parents, and families / whanau use information...and document learning experiences...in ways that improve children's learning, as well as communication about and reflection on that learning”*. (p.5). This quote makes me think about one of my queries for this research: How did my current practice of using Information Technology in my early childhood centre support the mana mauri and wairua of the children, the center, my participants and myself? Here, Ministry Of Education, 2009 explains that using IT in early childhood can be directed towards enhancing teaching but also support children’s identities, cultures, mana and learning through interactive learning opportunities and documentation of such experiences.

Conversely, the negative impact of using IT with young children has emerged as another theme during my research. There is a huge potential to use technology in early childhood education. However, this has become an area of great controversy. During the last decade, many studies have shown that computer use promotes children's behavior problems and can have negative impacts on their learning abilities and development (Pohio, 2009,). Various researchers have suggested that these negative effects depend not only on the amount of time spent with technology but also on children's age, gender and personality, adult’s use and understanding of the tools. (Siraj-Blatchford & Siraj-Blatchford, 2003 and Fletcher-Flinn & Suddendorf, 1998). A research by Keumala, Yoestara & Putri, (2019) found that alot of young children using digital tools developed an addiction to the screen resulting in attention span shortage, short temperament, speech delays, delays in motor skill development due to less physical activity and introductory cause of child depression. Flayer, (2009), also found the exact same results in their research that, “ICT significantly hampers the language development of the children and at the same time weakens the sociability nature”. The author, Keumala, Yoestara & Putri, (2019) state, “Attention deficit and mental disorder are also found in this study. Children tend to not care about their surroundings when they are using gadgets” and also quotes Sundus, (2018) to back their findings, “Sundus (2018) states that too much gadget use introduces depression in children of certain ages which also leads to

mental health issues in childhood and adolescence” (p.324). Another study by (Sinha, 2007) also claims that the use of computers and other electronic devices seriously impairs children's ability to develop naturally. Another statement arguing that computers are not developmentally suitable for young children since they learn via their bodies, according to one reason against introducing ICT to them early focused on why ICT should not be introduced to children in early years (Haugland 2000). These studies also state that having positive or negative effects is directly linked to how supervised the use of technology is and how it is utilised by adults or teachers in the room. Relating back to the findings of Pohio, 2009, Siraj-Blatchford & Siraj-Blatchford, 2003, Sundus, 2003, the research by Keumala, Yoestara & Putri, (2019) suggests that in order to fully take advantage of the opportunities that ICT presents for enhancing all facets of early childhood education practise, teachers need support, guidance, and opportunities to become capable, competent, and informed about the educational role and potential of ICT.

Another theme that I noticed is the place of IT in the early childhood teaching and learning environment and in my review was the fact that teachers had different opinions on how they felt about Information technology as a teaching tool. According to a research by (Hudson & Hess, 2011), some teachers think that it was very useful to have IT in preschools and schools while others did not agree with this statement. In addition, some teachers believed that there was little evidence to suggest whether or not it would benefit young children when compared with traditional methods such as paper and pencil exercises or hands-on activities (Hudson & Hess, 2011). When we discussed about the positive impacts of IT in ece, I noticed that a lot of papers including Herodotou, (2018), Ramsey (2006), Ministry Of Education, (2005) & (2009), and Pohio, (2009) mention that the impact of IT on young children is depends on the role of adults/teachers present during these experiences. In the research by Pohio, (2009), they mention that **use of IT with children is directly linked to teacher’s perspective, theories and understanding of the tools.** They support their claim by referencing Visser, (2000), “benefits of the computer [or other ICT resources] are entirely dependent on the pedagogical approach of the adults, and the teaching strategies that are put into place accordingly the decisions the adults make will determine learning outcomes for children” (p.11). It was interesting to note that socio-cultural approach is an evident factor in defining teacher’s use of IT with children as they may use these technologies based on their

own understanding, pedagogical approaches, style and theories of teaching. In addition to this, Laffey (2004) also believes that the availability of IT depends in part on the teachers' opinions of it and their level of familiarity, confidence with it. Pohio, (2009) also quotes various theories and researches by Patterson (2004) who claims that this inturn shall enhance children's learning. I can use this particular research to understand how did my current practice of using information technology in my early childhood centre support the mana mauri and wairua of the children, the center, my participants and myself. Certainly, this claim opens the door for new opportunities in professional development and learning for teachers as they may realize the impact their perspective put on the use of IT. As explained by Siraj-Blatchford and Whitebread, (2003), teachers and parents can refer to the Developmentally Appropriate Technology in Early Childhood (DATEC) when deciding whether or not IT applications are acceptable for young children and on ways to use them: Applications should: be educational; promote cooperation; integrate and play using ICT; allow the child to take charge; be transparent and intuitive; not include violence or stereotyping; raise awareness of health and safety problems; and engage parents in their children's education. This allows me to look at my current IT tools and practices and notice if they are suitable for children in early childhood. As Brown, 2007, said, this provokes teachers to critically review their own practices, perspective and learn about alternative approaches for deeper learning.

Finally, difference in parent's opinions on the use of information technology has been observed as another common theme among these papers. *Te Whaariki* values the knowledge, experiences and ideas families bring to their child's learning, "the wider world of family and community is an integral part of the early childhood curriculum" (p. 42) (MOE,2017). It is important to understand how IT is seen by whanau and what parents expect from these tools in early childhood environment. According to the results of Siraj-Blatchford and Siraj-Blatchford (2006), "children's computer use in schools or early childhood settings is directly impacted by their out of school experiences" (p. 56). Furthermore, the level of IT competence gained by children at home is determined by a variety of circumstances, including access to equipment, assistance for learning how to use it, and the specific interests and aptitudes of older family members (Siraj-Blatchford & Siraj-Blatchford, 2006, Pohio, 2009). This means that how the family members perceive IT, use and understand it, determines children's learning of digital tools. This also directs us in understanding what the parents think of digital technology in early childhood education. In their study of technology

use in early childhood centers, Gjelaj, Buza, Shatri, and Zabeli (2020) report that parents believe that children having early access to technology will promote their school readiness. However, around 57 percent of them do not support this relationship. It is important to note that these findings are not new—many studies have reported similar results. Wood (2008) study found that parents believed that using technology would help children develop social skills and problem-solving abilities more quickly than those who did not use it. Specht (2011) study found similar results: parents thought their children would be able to learn while they used technology. However, other studies suggest that parents may look at the negative effects of excessive screen time on children's development or behavior. Wood et al.'s (2008) study found that many parents felt that children may develop behavioral problems because they were in front of a screen too much and develop problems including addiction to screen, sleeping problems, physical development delays while they also think that children miss an outdoor play with their peers (p.173). However, Gjelaj, Buza, Shatri, and Zabeli (2020), found in their research that parents encourage the practice of introducing their children to technological tool, citing “only if it benefits their children's growth” (p.173).

3. Conclusion

This literature review focused on four major themes that have been observed: Positive effects, negative effects of IT in early childhood, place of IT in early childhood and teacher's perspectives, parents understanding and perspectives on the topic. I have observed that in all the articles that discuss the aspects of my topic, repeatedly mention that the use, understanding, and child's learning is highly dependant on the user (here teacher) and their interactions with the technology. This theory connects us to the socio-cultural theories by Vgotsky and Bronfenbrenner, with a conclusion that both teacher and parents understanding of digital tools is dependent on “Vygotsky's ideas that learning leads development and occurs in relationships with people, places and things, mediated by participation in valued social and cultural activities” (Ministry Of Education, 2017, p.61) and that these values will create an impact on children's learning. This calls for a reflective and analytical practice for teachers where they repeatedly reflect on their pedagogical approaches, style and theories of teaching, specially relating to IT use in early childhood centers. This prompts me to review the following questions I developed at the beginning of my research: What does the literature say about Information Technology in early childhood centers? What have I learned about my

existing practice of using Information Technology in my early childhood centre? How did my current practice of using Information Technology in my early childhood centre support the mana mauri and wairua of the children, the center, my participants and myself? Through research tools like observations and interviews along with literature analysis on the expected practices and data synopsis, I shall be able to learn about my current practice and plan for intervention stage. Particulary, Pohio, 2009 and Siraj-Blatchford, 2003, 2006 has pushed me to understand my practices from an unbiased/sterotypical lens and look from the perspective of children's learning and not my own understanding of what's right and wrong. For my intervention phase, I shall reflect on my practice, look at different theories, test them and review articles with my teaching team (Intervention is not limited to these ideas).

4. References

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